

Streamlining the translation and exchange workflow for STACK exercises

Michael Kallweit¹

Abstract: The IDIAM project, funded by Erasmus+, is a collaboration between five European universities to develop interactive digital assessment tools in mathematics. The project focuses on the development of materials for the assessment of competences in STEM, in particular in mathematics. Within the scope of the IDIAM initiative, STACK exercises from the HELM workbooks are subject to translation. The utilization of Moodle's multi-language content filter enables the embedding of various translations directly into the questions themselves, which subsequently facilitates their wide distribution.

This article will delve into the translation and sharing workflow of STACK questions, highlighting the diverse range of tools created to streamline the process. The author will introduce tools specifically designed to handle XML export files and embedded HTML seamlessly, ensuring compatibility with learning management systems remains intact. The objective is to establish a standardized format for a golden copy, which enables effortless tracking of various translations and modifications within a version control system.

Keywords: multilanguage content; translation; question exchange; version control; xml; STACK

1 Introduction and Motivation

The IDIAM projekt (Interactive digital assessment in mathematics) includes, among other things, both software and pedagogical development work packages to develop interactive problem sets in foundations of algebra and calculus and multivariate analysis for engineering students. The programming work packages aim to develop interactive 2D and 3D lightweight graphics in STACK and interactive adaptive questions. The project aims to expand the community working on digital assessment in mathematics by involving more faculty members within the partner institutions through local seminars and online experience sharing. The project will make the developed software and question sets accessible to other educational institutions and countries through open licenses and different languages, thus providing added value at EU level. An important source of content in one sub-project is the HELM (Helping Engineers Learn Mathematics) workbooks, which provide flexible learning resources to support engineering students in learning mathematics and statistics. In a recent effort, the exercises from the workbooks have been transformed into STACK questions [ZNDM21]. Exercises from some of these workbooks will be translated as part of the project.

¹ Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Fakultät für Mathematik, Universitätsstr. 150 , 44780 Bochum, Germany
michael.kallweit@rub.de

1.1 Enhancing question exchange

Despite the vast quantity of STACK questions and question banks already developed², most of these resources are only utilized in a one-way manner: On the one hand, tasks are developed in projects and then made available to others, but without being updated again. On the other hand, many educators only make use of databases without posting their own contributions. This represents a significant missed opportunity, as these resources could potentially be shared and reused, thereby maximizing their value and impact. Against this backdrop, our goal is to create the conditions that enable effective exchange of STACK questions. By fostering an environment where questions can be easily shared, modified, and reused, we can significantly enhance the efficiency and versatility of the question creation process and reduce the time and effort required to create new questions.

Potential strategies to achieve this goal could include the establishment of a central repository for STACK questions, the development of standardized formats and workflows for question exchange, and the implementation of systems that facilitate easy searching and retrieval of questions³. One of the most important aspects of this is the ability to version the questions so that changes of them are transparent to all users.

The recent introduction of Moodle 4 has brought a slew of innovative features that serve to further enhance the user experience. Among these, one of the most significant improvements pertains to the management of question and managing their versions within the question bank. However, the exchange of questions, especially across different universities, remains challenging. Unfortunately, there is no easy way to view the specific changes made to questions or to compare versions.

We address this problem in one of the steps of our proposed workflow.

1.2 Multi-language content

By enabling the creation and display of course content in multiple languages, Moodle is equipped to meet the diverse linguistic needs of educators and students across the globe. If you want to use teaching and learning materials of another language and translate them into your own language, you have basically two possibilities: you create a translated copy of the materials or you can integrate the different translations within. We follow the latter approach and provide a brief overview of the possibilities for this.

Moodle Multi-language content filter

Moodle incorporates a robust multi-language content filter that allows instructors to create

² e.g. Abacus material bank (<https://abacus.aalto.fi/>)

³ e.g. DOMAIN - database for digital tasks in mathematics (<http://db.ak-mathe-digital.de/>)

course content in multiple languages. This feature is a testament to Moodle's commitment to catering to a global and diverse user base. The filter works by displaying only the content that matches the language preferences of the user or the system settings. This personalized display ensures that each user has access to course content in a language they are comfortable with, thereby enhancing comprehension and engagement.

The multi-language content filter operates using language tags. These tags are used to identify the language of specific sections of text or other course content, see figure 1. By marking the content in this way, the filter can accurately discern which sections to display based on the user's language settings.

```
<span lang="en" class="multilang"> Hello World </span>  
<span lang="de" class="multilang"> Hallo Welt </span>  
<span lang="no" class="multilang"> Hei Verden </span>
```

Fig. 1: Example of the moodle Multi-language content filter

The flexibility and utility of Moodle's multi-language content filter extends beyond the main content of a course. It can also be applied to the headings of activities and the titles of questions, further enhancing the multilingual capabilities of Moodle. However, it's important to note that this feature comes with potential drawbacks. Specifically, the use of the multi-language filter can impact site performance.

Multi-Language Content (v2)

An alternative to the standard multi-language content filter in Moodle is the Multi-language Content (v2) filter. This enhanced version of the filter offers several advantages that may make it more suitable for certain contexts. One of the key features of this filter is its use of simple, non-HTML tags to mark multi-language blocks, see figure 2. This approach simplifies the tagging process and reduces the potential for HTML-related errors.

```
{mlang en} Hello World {mlang}  
{mlang de} Hallo Welt {mlang}  
{mlang no} Hei Verden {mlang}
```

Fig. 2: Example of the moodle multi-Language Content (v2) filter

The Multi-language Content (v2) filter is compatible with both the Multi-Language Content Atto plugin and the Multi-Language Content TinyMCE plugin. This compatibility ensures a seamless integration with popular text editors used in Moodle, thereby providing users with a flexible and user-friendly environment for creating multi-language content.

STACK language blocks

An important development in recent versions of STACK, starting from version 4.4.2, is the addition of language blocks. These blocks allow for more precise language management

within STACK questions. A language block is used by enclosing text within language-specific code tags, effectively marking that text as pertaining to a particular language, see figure 3.

```
[[lang code='en']] Hello World [[/lang]]  
[[lang code='de']] Hallo Welt [[/lang]]  
[[lang code='no']] Hei Verden [[/lang]]
```

Fig. 3: Example of STACK language blocks

One of the key features of this system is their compatibility with inline CASText2. This means that language blocks can be used within all fields of the STACK question edit form, where CASText2 is used, in particular, in the construction of the answer options for multiple choice questions.

Despite all the advantages of the newer systems, we will use the conventional filter in the following, since it can also be used detached from STACK for other question types in Moodle.

2 Workflow and tools

The process of creating and updating STACK questions, particularly over multiple iterations, can be a tedious and time-consuming task. This challenge is further compounded when adding translations, especially in collaborative development of questions. The resulting complexity can place a significant burden on educators and administrators. With this in mind, our primary goal is to minimize human effort and simplify or automate as much of this process as possible.

The proposed workflow is a five-step process designed to enhance collaboration and efficiency:

1. Extracting the questions from moodle
2. Splitting the questions into individual files
3. Translating the strings inside the questions
4. Prettifying the XML
5. Committing to a repository

To achieve the goal of minimizing human effort in creating and updating STACK questions, a suite of tools has been developed⁴. These tools each serve a distinct function in the process, contributing to a more streamlined and efficient workflow.

⁴ The source code of all tools can be found under <https://github.com/m-r-k/stack2023>

2.1 Extracting the questions from moodle

Moodle offers two primary methods for extracting questions: through a course backup (mbz) and through export from the question bank (xml). The Moodle XML format is a proprietary structure designed specifically for the import and export of questions to be used with the Quiz module. Despite being a Moodle-specific format, it exhibits interoperability with other learning management systems. For instance, ILIAS is capable of importing STACK Questions in Moodle XML format.

On the other hand, the Moodle Backup File (MBZ) is an archive that comprises a compressed version of an entire Moodle course. This format can be used to restore a complete course within the Moodle platform. It's important to note that the structure and the kind of information contained in an MBZ file differ from those in an XML file. While the XML file primarily concerns quiz questions, the MBZ file encapsulates a broader spectrum of course information.

We have developed a tool, called `convert_mbz`, which facilitates the extraction of questions from a Moodle course backup and their conversion into the Moodle XML format.

2.2 Splitting the questions into individual files

In the context of managing a large question bank, we propose the storage of each question in individual XML files. This approach offers numerous benefits that streamline question handling and enhance collaborative efforts.

Firstly, maintaining individual XML files for each question facilitates effective change tracking. By leveraging version control systems such as Git, modifications to each question can be easily monitored and recorded over time. This granular level of tracking ensures a comprehensive audit trail of changes and enhances the transparency of question revisions. Secondly, separate XML files for each question significantly reduce the likelihood of merge conflicts when collaborating in teams. By isolating each question in its own file, simultaneous edits to different questions do not clash, thereby minimizing the necessity for conflict resolution and improving the efficiency of collaborative work. Thirdly, this method promotes modularity and reusability. With each question contained in a separate file, it is easier to combine, share, and transfer questions. This approach effectively transforms each question into a standalone module that can be inserted, removed, or rearranged without disrupting the integrity of the entire question bank. Lastly, individual XML files for each question simplify the debugging process. Should an error occur, it is localized within a single file, making it easier to identify and rectify the issue without sifting through an extensive collection of questions.

For splitting a Moodle XML file with a bunch of questions, we developed the tool `split_exported_xml`.

2.3 Translating the strings inside the questions

Adding translations to a STACK question is an essential task in creating a multilingual learning environment. However, the process for doing so can vary greatly in terms of efficiency and user-friendliness. A less favorable method involves using the Moodle Edit Question Interface. While this method is technically feasible, it can be cumbersome and time-consuming, especially when dealing with a large number of questions or complex question structures. A slightly more efficient method involves using the exported question as XML files and adding translations using a text editor. This method provides greater flexibility and control over the translation process. However, it requires a degree of technical knowledge of the XML format and can still be quite labor-intensive.

So we came up with an even more efficient and user-friendly method, which involves the use of a spreadsheet for adding translations. This approach allows for easy input and editing of translations in a familiar and intuitive format.

The tool `xml2csv` functions by extracting translations, denoted by the span-tags, from a Moodle XML file to a CSV file, along with a template file. This CSV file organizes different strings in rows and their corresponding translations in columns, providing a clear and structured overview of the translations, see figure 4. This format allows educators to conveniently make modifications to the translations using any spreadsheet application.

	A	B	C	D
	Nummer	de	en	no
2	###1###		:Exercise	:Øving
3	###2###		:Complete the table of values for the function $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$ for x between $\{c\}$ and $\{c\}$.	:Fyller tabellen med verdier for funksjonen $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$ for x mellom $\{c\}$ og $\{c\}$.
4	###3###		:From the table of values, what is the shape of the function $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$?	:Basert på tabellverdiene, hva er formen til funksjonen $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$?
5	###4###		:Graph A	:Graf A
6	###5###		:Graph B	:Graf B
7	###6###		:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[1],"Graph A")@}	:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[1],"Graf A")@}
8	###7###		:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[2],"Graph B")@}	:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[2],"Graf B")@}
9	###8###		:Graph C	:Graf C
10	###9###		:Graph D	:Graf D
11	###10###		:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[3],"Graph C")@}	:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[3],"Graf C")@}
12	###11###		:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[4],"Graph D")@}	:{@thumbnailplot(funcstoplot[4],"Graf D")@}
13	###12###		:We fill in the values in the table by substituting the value of x into the function expression $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$.	:Vi fyller verdiene inn i tabellen ved å substituere x i med en gitt verdi i funksjonsuttrykket $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$.
14	###13###		:Hence:	:Altså:
15	###14###		:To find the graph of $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$, you plot the $\{x\}$ and $\{f(x)\}$ points on a graph and pick the graph that is close to your sketch.	:For å finne grafen for $f(x) = \{f(x)\}$ må du plote $\{x\}$ og $\{f(x)\}$ punktene på en graf og velge grafen som er nærmest skissen din.

Fig. 4: Spreadsheet with automatic extracted language strings and an extra empty column for a new language to be filled by the user

Once the modifications are complete, the tool `csv2xml` comes into play. This script takes the updated translations from the CSV file and re-integrates them into a new Moodle XML file. This seamless back-and-forth conversion between XML and CSV greatly simplifies the process of managing translations, making it more efficient and less prone to errors.

We can even go one step further and save even more time by using machine translation to

2.5 Committing to a repository

In terms of managing questions and their versions, it seems that there is a broad consensus: version control is the way forward. Version control systems like Git provide robust solutions for tracking changes, managing revisions, and facilitating collaboration, which are all vital in the context of managing a large question bank. The decentralized way of organizing repositories accommodates a global exchange, where there is no single central location.

Indeed, the final step in the workflow process involves committing the prettified XML files to a Git repository. However, even within this process, there are several factors that need careful consideration.

A key point of debate is how to structure the repository. One approach could involve maintaining separate branches for each institution. This could facilitate a more tailored and personalized approach to question management, allowing individual institutions to adapt the questions to their specific needs and standards. An alternative approach could be to maintain branches for each language addition. This would prioritize multilingual accessibility, ensuring that questions are readily available in multiple languages. However, this approach may also present challenges, particularly in managing and coordinating translations across different branches. But thanks to the prettify, changes should be easily merged.

3 Future work

Looking towards the future, there are several areas of focus that could further improve the management of Moodle questions. It is universally acknowledged that a sensible organization of multilingual questions is critical for ensuring the efficiency and effectiveness of the system. This organization is particularly important in an era of globalization and increased diversity, where questions may need to be accessed and understood by people from a range of linguistic backgrounds.

We would like to incorporate the prettify script as part of the tidy up process in STACK. This could help to enhance the clarity and comprehensibility of questions, and their use could greatly improve the process of question management in version control systems.

Bibliography

- [ZNDM21] Zerva, Konstantina; Nicholson, Ilyas; Doña Mateo, Adrián: , Translating the HELM workbooks to STACK. <https://stack-assessment.org/CaseStudies/2021/HELM/>, 2021. [Online; accessed 2023-05-22].